

Dynamical Analysis of Composite Beams Subject to Compressive Load

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Abstract

Analyzing the dynamical behavior of composite beams under compressive loads involves considering various factors such as material properties, geometry, boundary conditions, and loading conditions. The dynamic response of a composite beam can be studied using analytical methods, numerical simulations, or experimental testing. Composite materials often involve layers of different materials with distinct properties. Composite beams with different materials are used in many application areas, with the particular advantage of providing lightness, high strength and customized mechanical properties. During the design phase, it is important to perform a careful engineering analysis to minimize incompatibilities and potential problems between materials. Transition regions between different materials ensure a homogeneous material transition and reduce incompatibilities between materials. These regions help reduce stress concentrations that may occur in material transitions. Besides, it is considered whether the compressive load applied to the composite beam is constant or varies with time. The equation of motion for the composite beam based on appropriate structural mechanics principles is derived. The differential equation is solved to obtain the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the composite beam.

Keywords: Composite beam, dynamical analysis, Euler-Bernoulli beam

Introduction

Innovations in various engineering fields, materials science and structural design have enabled the development of stronger, lighter and more hardness structural elements. The most important of these innovations are composite beams created by combining various materials. Composite beams impress as structural components that show superior performance, especially under compressive loads. these structural members provide higher strength and hardness than single-strength beams by gathering different material mechanical properties. In order to minimize incompatibilities and possible problems between materials during the design phase, a careful engineering analysis should be performed. The behavior of composite beams subjected to compressive loads is of critical importance, especially in terms of buckling and stability. Understanding how structural elements behave under these loads is a fundamental requirement for the design of safe and sustainable structures. In this context, both experimental studies and numerical analyzes are important tools to determine the load-carrying capacities, deformations and failure modes of composite beams.

Recently, engineering structures attract great attention from many researchers. The design of these structures is very important to increase their performance and extend their hardness. The solutions to such problems that we encounter in real life are quite complex and difficult.

A mathematical model is developed to investigate the behavior of a structure close to the real problem. There are many studies in the literature about beam structures with different mathematical models [1]. These types of models are in the form of linear or non-linear partial differential equations or integro differential equations dependent on spatial and time. Linear models are considered as a first approximation. However, since linear modeling is insufficient to explain some physical phenomena encountered in reality, non-linear models have been proposed. Thus, a better connection between real events is established. Nonlinearity may have a structure that is cubic, quadratic, or both. In addition, the solution of the equations is affected by the difference in boundary conditions as well as the difference in the models. It is difficult to obtain the exact solution of a nonlinear model under boundary conditions [1].

Composite beams play an important role in the analysis of complex dynamic systems encountered in fields such as engineering and physics [2]. Kocatürk and Akbaş [3] investigated the dynamic behavior of axial functionally graded beams under the influence of live harmonic loading and showed how material grading affects the response of composite beams under dynamic loading conditions. Their findings contributed to a better understanding of the dynamic performance and stability of composite beams, especially in situations involving travelling loads and varying axial forces. One of the studies on the free vibration analysis of delaminated composite beams under axial load was carried out by Della [4]. This study examines in detail the effects of delaminations on the dynamic behavior of beams. Della used analytical methods to determine the effects of delaminations in composite beams on free vibration frequencies.

In this study, the dynamic behavior of composite beams subjected to compressive load will be analyzed. Additionally, the performance characteristics of different composite materials and their potential benefits in structural applications will be discussed. By integrating these analytical approaches and findings, engineers and researchers can develop more effective design strategies and predictive models to improve the performance and safety of composite structures in practical applications.

Equation of Motion

The equation of motion of an Euler Bernoulli beam subjected to axially loaded is introduced as [1]

$$(E I \tilde{w}'')'' + (P \tilde{w}')' + \rho A \ddot{\tilde{w}} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. A composite beam subject to compressive load

where E , I , P represent the modulus of elasticity, the moment of inertia and the axial load, respectively. A is cross-sectional area, ρ is density of beam material. $w(x, t)$ corresponds to the displacement. (\prime) , $(\dot{})$ indicate the derivative with respect to spatial (\tilde{x}) and time (\tilde{t}), respectively. The problem considered is a composite beam formed by the combination of two different materials. Such problems can be called layered composite material problems. This problem has the partial differential equation with variable coefficients. The analytical solution of this type of equation is difficult. For this reason, semi-analytical or approximate solutions are needed. In order to overcome these difficulties, the beam can be divided into two regions and fourth order linear partial differential equation with constant coefficients can be written for each region.

$$E I \tilde{w}_1^{iv} + \tilde{P} \tilde{w}_1'' + \rho A \ddot{\tilde{w}}_1 = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$E I \tilde{w}_2^{iv} + \tilde{P} \tilde{w}_2'' + \rho A \ddot{\tilde{w}}_2 = 0 \quad (3)$$

These two equations are homogeneous, no special solution is required. Since we divided the equation into two, we need to the transition conditions as well as the boundary conditions.

Boundary conditions:

$$\tilde{w}_1(0, \tilde{t}) = 0$$

$$\tilde{w}_1''(0, \tilde{t}) = 0$$

Transition conditions:

$$\tilde{w}_1(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \tilde{w}_2(x_1, \tilde{t})$$

$$\tilde{w}_1'(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \tilde{w}_2'(x_1, \tilde{t})$$

$$\tilde{w}_1''(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \alpha_{E_2} \tilde{w}_2''(x_1, \tilde{t})$$

$$\tilde{w}_1'''(x_1, \tilde{t}) + P \tilde{w}_1'(x_1, \tilde{t}) = \alpha_{E_2} \tilde{w}_2'''(x_1, \tilde{t}) + P \tilde{w}_2'(x_1, \tilde{t}) \quad (4)$$

Boundary conditions:

$$\tilde{w}_1(1, \tilde{t}) = 0$$

$$\tilde{w}_2''(0, \tilde{t}) = 0$$

The displacement and moment equal to zero in the simple-simple support. In the transition region, displacement, rotation and shearing forces are equal [4]. To get rid of shape and material dependency, non-dimensionalization is performed. Then, Eqs. (2)-(3) reduce to

$$w_1^{iv} + P w_1'' + \dot{w}_1 = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_{E_2} w_2^{iv} + P w_2'' + \alpha_{\rho_2} \dot{w}_2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

where new dimensionless terms are

$$w = \frac{\bar{w}_1 L}{r^2}, \quad t = \frac{\bar{t}}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{E_1 I_1}{\rho_1 A_1}}, \quad x = \frac{\bar{x}}{L}, \quad r = \sqrt{\frac{I_1}{A_1}}, \quad P = \bar{P} \frac{E_1 I_1}{L^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha_{E_2} = \frac{E_2}{E_1} \quad \alpha_{\rho_2} = \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1}$$

Solution Method

Assuming that the variation with time is harmonic, the solution for the equation in first region can be written as follows [2,4]

$$w_1(x, t) = X_1(x) e^{i\omega_n t} \quad (8)$$

Substituting the solution (8) to Eq. (5) yields

$$X_1^{iv}(x) + P X_1''(x) - \omega_n^2 X_1(x) = 0 \quad (9)$$

Similarly, the solution for second region is suggested as

$$w_2(x, t) = X_2(x) e^{i\omega_n t} \quad (10)$$

Substituting the solution (10) to q. (6) gives

$$\alpha_{E_2} X_2^{iv}(x) + P X_2''(x) - \alpha_{\rho_2} \omega_n^2 X_2(x) = 0 \quad (11)$$

If the boundary and transition conditions are rearranged, then

$$\begin{aligned} X_1(0) &= 0 & X_1(x_1) &= X_2(x_1) & X_2(1) &= 0 \\ X_1''(0) &= 0 & X_1'(x_1) &= X_2'(x_1) & X_2''(1) &= 0 \\ & & X_1(x_1) &= \alpha_{E_2} X_2''(x_1) & & \\ X_1'''(x_1) + P X_1'(x_1) &= \alpha_{E_2} X_2'''(x_1) + P X_2'(x_1) & & & & \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

are obtained. The solution of Eq. (9) is in the form

$$X_1(x) = c_i e^{r_i x} \quad (13)$$

where roots of the characteristic equation are

$$r_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\sqrt{P^2 + 4\omega_n^2} - 2P}}{2} \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the solution of equation (11) is

$$X_2(x) = a_i e^{b_i x} \quad (15)$$

where the roots of the characteristic equation are

$$b_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\alpha_{E_2}(-P + \sqrt{4\alpha_{E_2}\alpha_{\rho_2} + \omega_n^2 + P^2})}}{2\alpha_{E_2}} \quad (16)$$

Numerical Results

Table 1. The variation of natural frequencies, ω_n for steel and copper ($\alpha_{E_2} = \frac{12}{21}$, $\alpha_{\rho_2} = \frac{451}{785}$)

x_1	0,2	0,4	0,6	0,8
$P = 0$	9.783455806	9.622617700	9.632163536	9.807019116
$P = 5$	35.55536971	36.68831714	36.82466784	36.72443225

Table 2. The variation of critical value of P for $\omega_n=0$ ($\alpha_{E_2} = \frac{12}{21}$, $\alpha_{\rho_2} = \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1} = \frac{451}{785}$)

x_1	0,2	0,4	0,6	0,8
P	5.754655523	6.419645962	7.876906101	9.496305058

Table 3. The variation of natural frequencies, ω_n for steel and titanium ($\alpha_{E_2} = \frac{11}{21}$, $\alpha_{\rho_2} = \frac{246}{785}$)

x_1	0,2	0,4	0,6	0,8
$P = 0$	12.30904117	10.90855439	10.01170877	9.845328884
$P = 6$	40.27878043	40.49687418	39.32566731	36.15652711

Table 4. The variation of critical value of P for $\omega_n=0$ ($\alpha_{E_2} = \frac{11}{21}$, $\alpha_{\rho_2} = \frac{246}{785}$)

x_1	0,2	0,4	0,6	0,8
P	5.286493251	5.967417602	7.526628160	9.413963852

Conclusion

Considering the numerical results, the axial load value increases as the cross-sectional length of first region increases. The critical load value is the smallest value, P that enforces the structure to buckle. When it exceeds this load value, the structure loses its stability. Lower displacements are expected at larger natural frequency values. As the critical load value increases, it is seen that the natural frequency values decrease. If the natural frequency is zero, it is observed to what extent the critical axial load decreases.

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